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MISOGYNY IN POLITICS: FEMINIST CRITICISM AND ITS ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS (REGARDING THE TREATMENT OF REPUBLICAN WOMEN)

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Introduction

Gender discrimination has long been a key issue in political and social debates. However, practice shows that even self-proclaimed advocates of equality and inclusion often demonstrate blatant double standards. This is especially evident when it comes to Republican women. Despite their accomplishments and contributions to political life, they are not only politically criticized, but also attacked for their appearance, style choices, or even their personal lives. This text explores the phenomenon of reverse sexism and its manifestations in American politics, where appearance and affiliation with a certain ideology become a reason to discredit them.

Section 1: The Problem of Criticizing Republican Women in the Media

A recent video essay entitled “*Why Do Republican Women Look Like That?*” [1] was yet another example of misogyny in the liberal camp. In it, the author blatantly condemns Republican women for their appearance, linking it to their political beliefs. This approach is not only unethical, but also undermines the principles of inclusiveness that liberals so often proclaim. As the video notes, images of Republican women are viewed through the lens of “traditional femininity,” which, according to the author, supposedly makes them symbols of patriarchy [1]. What is ignored, however, is the fact that these women consciously choose their strategies to appeal to their audiences.

An article by Rebecca Traister of *New York Magazine* adds fuel to the fire. She writes: “*The brutal irony of women on the right is that their emergence as mighty politicians is reliant entirely on feminist gains, and their experiences track with the feminist critique of inequality, including expectations of acquiescence to powerful men*” [13]. In passive-aggressive manner, the female journalist herself resorts to abusive “you’re nothing without me” gaslighting, attributing the merits of individual women to the ephemeral higher power (deity?) of feminism. If a man were to come “from above” in his accusatory criticism in this way, it appears unlikely that a female journalist would be delighted by such paternalism (*maternalism*, in her case), and even in such a nasty, patronizing tone.

However, this journalist is not embarrassed by anything. Without noticing, she calls Trump — “*a serial adulterer who had cheated on two of his wives and was married to a woman who appeared to be his ideal: a simulacrum of every sculpted, shiny, glittery, enhanced expectation of femininity. Here was a man who regarded women with wolf-whistling lasciviousness or dismissed them as pigs and dogs*” [13]. What precise formulations, how much venom and hatred of women they contain.

She herself writes about female colleagues and female politicians from the opposite side of the spectrum as (consumer products for contemplation and service to the gaze — only not to the male gaze, but to the author of the column, presenting her own view): “*But if the sleek women of Fox were one model of idealized feminine aesthetics, this era demands a different look, one constructed not to Ailes’s tastes but to Trump*” [13]. This position clearly demonstrates a discriminatory approach that reduces politics to appearance, neglecting women’s professional achievements.

Vanessa Friedman’s article from *The New York Times* [4], which discusses the changes in South Dakota Governor Kristi Noem’s appearance — which she dismissively refers to as ‘*The Trumpification*’, is particularly revealing [4]. The author focuses attention on her “new teeth” and hairstyle, suggesting that this is done to please a male audience [4]. Such comments not only ignore Noem’s policy initiatives, including her border security efforts, but also represent an example of petty, superficial criticism.

Section 2: The political image of women, reverse sexism and the hypocrisy of liberals

Misogyny against Republican women is not just an incident. It is a systemic phenomenon that reflects reverse sexism and internalized misogyny. Liberals who claim to fight for inclusivity ignore these principles when confronted with women who have different views. For example, accusations that Republican women are “*bedfellows of the patriarchy*” are reinforced by misogynistic attacks on their style of dress and appearance.

This is particularly evident in the criticism of Nikki Haley for her love of skirts and heels. *The Fashion of GOP Politics: How Republican Women Are Dressing to Change America*, by Priya Shah of *Columbia Political Review* [12], emphasizes that Haley uses traditional femininity as a way to balance her personal identity with the expectations of her audience. If the title itself doesn’t suggest that the article is ridiculously “*feminine*” in terms of emphasis and priorities (in the sense that normal people wouldn’t even

bother with this sort of thing, but the female author is building a whole conspiracy around someone else's closet) [12].

Haley's choice of outfits is interpreted by a gender critic as follows:

“Moreover, Haley's love of high heels highlighted her commitment to traditional femininity. She wore heels to show endurance and avoid downplaying her gender, hoping to appear like a familiar but unthreatening figure of female authority” [12]. Also, very unprofessional in our opinion, is the way in which decisions about the visual image and appearance of a female politician by the same female author are indiscriminately mixed with Haley's political position (supposedly there is some correlation between the color of a bag or shoes and views on this or that social issue — it is not perceived as serious criticism, but rather as personal animosity):

“As a female Republican, she has also called herself a “consensus” candidate who hopes to make abortion laws appeasable to multiple audiences through compromise and discussion. The label only confirms the message her clothing sends: she is a woman, but not a radical one. In her campaign announcement, Haley also said that she “did not believe in glass ceilings,” claiming that women could achieve anything if they put in the effort. — By the way, liberals never want to explain what is wrong with this statement, and why enough work and effort cannot help a woman in the modern Western world achieve absolutely anything she wants. — Throughout her career, she has denied using identity politics, but Haley uses her wardrobe to embody the mom-politician duality by either emphasizing or masking her identity as a woman depending on the pertinent political issue to which she must respond” [12].

Another example is Candace Owens [8]. Despite her successful career, she is under attack for her conservative views. She is accused of betraying race and supporting patriarchy, ignoring her strong stance on defending traditional values. These examples show that double standards are often used to discredit conservative women. She was fired from the Daily Wire for her insufficiently pro-Israel stance on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, and was threatened by the Jewish Orthodox Rabbi Shmuley when it was unpopular to

support her [7]. She was also deplatformed from YouTube. Nevertheless, she continues to run her blog and even supports her recently dismissed young colleague from the Daily Wire, Brett Cooper. This is a form of female solidarity that some feminists might envy [6].

Appearance in politics is not just a matter of aesthetics, but a powerful communication tool. For women politicians, it often becomes a way of adapting to the double standards, allowing them to simultaneously declare their professional competence and meet social expectations. According to the theory of symbolic interactionism, appearance is an important element of self-presentation that shapes impressions and contributes to effective communication with voters.

Nikki Haley and Kristi Noem provide examples of how clothing and style help political figures emphasize their values and goals. Even Priya Shah notes: *“As the only female candidate who ran for the Republican nomination, Haley’s gender was apparent. To turn this distinction into an advantage, she wore skirts. While this logic may seem counterintuitive, Haley used her femininity to stand out from the men. Among the sea of black suits and red ties, her skirts made her inescapable from the audience’s gaze. Haley’s traditional clothing conveyed that she did not want to be mocked in the same way former Secretary of State Hillary Clinton was for wearing pantsuits during her 2016 presidential campaign”* [12]. Her choice of skirts and classic silhouettes allows her to stand out among her male colleagues and remain feminine, which contributes to a trustworthy image.

Kristi Noem, on the other hand, often chooses strict suits to emphasize her independence and professionalism. Her image has become a symbol of competence and determination. However, the media, including feminist columnists from *The New York Times* [4], instead of recognizing these strategies, focuses on her appearance, ignoring her actual achievements. This reflects the double standard faced by women in politics, where their imagebuilding efforts are interpreted in a hostile manner.

An example of the complexities of appearance is the case of Senator Kathy Britt, who wore a strict green shirt and a hoop with a cross for a public appearance. Her image was designed to reflect her commitment to Christian values and traditional roles, but it drew ridicule on satirical shows. As Priya Shah notes, such attacks highlight the gap between women's real efforts in politics and the public's perception of them [12].

Section 3: Nonconforming Women in American Politics and Journalism

Some female politicians and journalists go beyond stereotypes by refusing to conform to societal expectations. An example is Tulsi Gabbard, an Iraq War veteran and former Democratic Party member who later became a Trump sympathizer. Despite her credentials and experience, she is regularly attacked by the liberal media, accused of "working for the Kremlin" and deviating from the progressive agenda [3].

Another example is Susie Wiles, White House Chief of Staff under Trump, who has made significant strides behind the scenes in the political arena [3]. She is often described as rigorous and competent, but even she faces gender stereotypes that emphasize the difficult position for women in politics.

Candace Owens continues to be attacked for her conservative views [7–8]. Her critics ignore her efforts to defend traditional values, instead focusing on discrediting her personality. Liberal activists often accuse her of "betraying" race and supporting patriarchy for supporting Republican ideals, ignoring her own mission of defending traditional values and the right to free opinion even for members of supposedly unwanted "minorities" who refuse to bend to the agenda of American Democrats and the new left in politics [7].

Another case demonstrates how the topic of protection of transgender rights becomes a tool of aggression. Congresswoman Nancy Mace was also attacked by an LGBT activist who accused her of insufficiently protecting the rights of "transgender" children [5]. The politician said she was attacked by a

transgender rights advocate, who “started molesting” her outside her congressional office building. The attacker grabbed Mace’ arms with such force that she needed a bandage. In response, she stated: “*Violence and threats continue to prove our point. Women deserve to be safe*” — wrote the congresswoman, noting that aggression will not stop her fight for women’s rights [5]. Mace has been a vocal advocate for women’s safety and has tried to limit the use of women’s spaces by transgender people, despite pressure from radical far-left activists.

This case underscores the challenges faced by women who advocate for women’s safety and rights — in fact, what should have united Mace with feminists. While in reality, the latter have chosen to keep their mouths shut and stick to the liberal status quo, allowing biological men to invade women’s exclusive spaces and threaten their comfort and safety. Apparently, the only ones who do not fear “censorship” from the “progressive community” are precisely those in the Republican party [7].

In addition, female journalists who do not fit the mainstream agenda are criticized. For example, female journalists such as Liz Wheeler and Megyn Kelly have become symbols of an independent approach in the media, in the view of liberal feminists — “not typical of blondes who support the Republican Party” (sic!). Gone from major television stations — such as Fox News — they continue to evoke polarized evaluations because of their conservative views, hairstyles, outfits — in a word, views, style, presentation and delivery of information. Liberal critics reproach them for seeking popularity among right-wing audiences, overlooking their professionalism, the importance of their work, and their outreach to audiences unknown to mainstream center-left feminism.

These examples emphasize that women who dare to challenge the liberal consensus are often discredited for both their views and their choice of expression. Despite their successes, such women face attempts to suppress their voices in the public space.

Section 4: Parallels with the situation in Ukraine

A similar dynamic can be observed in Ukrainian politics. Journalists Svetlana Kryukova and Olesya Medvedeva, who worked for *Strana.ua*, were often attacked for their independent views [7]. In Medvedeva's case, her conventional beauty, "too red lips" and famous curls became a cause for criticism. Despite the fact that she left for Europe during a full-scale war, her continued blogging in Russian is endlessly hated by some Ukrainian patriots.

Diana Panchenko, on the other hand, is shamed for her ostentatiously attractive appearance, including discussions of her "silicone forms". At the same time, her stylists always select strictly business-like looks that match her status as a TV host of political shows. However, female colleagues such as Tatyana Mikitenko (known as "Ragulivna") regularly use Panchenko's appearance as a target for ridicule [9–11]. Mikitenko has not hesitated to publicly call her "naughty" (similar to the title of local Ukrainian author Panas Mirnyi's piece "Poviya" ("Naughty"), the video about which Panchenko filmed), and regularly criticizes her personal and professional qualities in her videos [11].

In one of the videos dedicated to Panchenko and Kryukova, Mikitenko accused them of being "media dishonesty" and "media escort" (as if it were the height of decency and decency for a journalist to use such expressions in public communication with her own and not her audience) [9–10]. However, one day Mikitenko herself also got a beating from her opponents. Her critics from among those she ridiculed called her a "saggy woman" who is "lazy to go to the gym" and receives grant funding — money from foundations [2]. These attacks were an example of reverse shaming, showing that misogyny is a weapon used by both sides of the conflict. This level of discourse, where women bash each other for their appearance and professional style, shows how difficult it is to maintain a professional reputation in an environment saturated with misogyny and double standards. These examples emphasize that the pressure on women journalists in Ukraine is not much different from the attacks on women in American politics, making the problem a global one.

Conclusion

Criticizing Republican women based on their appearance or style is not just a manifestation of sexism. It is a symptom of a deep cultural problem with a lack of respect for political opponents. Liberal rhetoric that proclaims inclusivity doesn't stand the test when it comes to women with conservative views. It is important to remember that the struggle for women's rights must include everyone, regardless of their beliefs. This is the only way to build a society free of discrimination and double standards.

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